

Peace Time

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<https://www.euronewsproject.org/2021/07/20/peace-time/>

The peace of Cateau-Cambrésis between France and Spain, leaving the latter power dominant in Italy after the decades-long Italian wars, was concluded on the 2nd and 3rd of April 1559. All that was left was to work out the details. Meanwhile (says Grand Duke Cosimo I to Lorenzo Pagni) let's party!

We have certainty of peace having been concluded between this Majesty [Felipe II de Austria] and the Most Christian King [Henri II de Valois] [...] We wish you to give news of it first to the wise men on our Secret Council, then arrange for public processions to be held in the city and throughout the entire state of Florence, and with the solemn masses we thank His Divine Majesty for such a gift and such tranquillity.

Habbiamo la certezza della pace conclusa infra questa Maestà [Felipe II de Austria] et la Christianissima [Henri II de Valois] [...] Vogliamo che datane parte prima a quei nostri savi del Consiglio Secreto, voi procuriate che per la Città e per tutto lo stato nostro di Fiorenza si faccino processioni publiche, et con le messe solenni si ringratii Sua Maestà divina per tanto dono et quiete

[April 8, 1559, MdP 210, fol. 53r, <https://mia.medici.org/Mia/index.html#/mia/document-entity/229>]

But for the actual documents to begin their itinerary around Europe, more than two more weeks went by. In France, nothing was left to chance, considering the stakes involved, as evinced in this careful narrative from this Paris newsletter:

"Paris, April 25th, 1659. Peace is assured; the courier brought it on Saturday evening and two leagues from here the parcel having been taken from his hands was brought to Chaville to Dom Antoine Pimentel who, after having deciphered the letters, sent the signed treaty to His Eminence [Cardinal Mazarin]"

Paris le 25^e avril 1659 710
L'apais est assuré le Courier l'apporta samedi au soir et a deux
heures dix le paquet ayant esté porté d'entre ses mains fut
porté à Gaucille adon au hoinc. Gimmukil qui apres avoir
de chiffre des lettres on envoie le traicte signé a son Eminence
qui n'a pas enore Juge a propos qu'elle fust publiée quoy que
ce matin on ayt tiré le canon de la Bastille dans l'esperance
nous saurons vne partie du detail l'indisposition de son
Eminence qui garde le lit despuis huit Jours ayant retardé
l'assemblée qui se doit tenir au Louvre pour mettre cette paix
au Jour cependant on assure que nous reservons seulement
quatre places dans l'Artois a savoir Arras, Bethune, Bapaume
et Hesdin et dans le Roussillon Perpignan et Collioure,
mais nous rendons toutes autres conquestes faites sur
les Ennemis despuis la declaration de la guerre faite en
l'année 1638 mesmes en Perque moyennant quelque desdoyage
en argent qui se voit de nous la republique d'Angleterre
et mesme que la France veuille aussi rendre Perpignan et
Collioure les Espagnols offrent de nous donner ainsy et
J'over cest tout ce que se publie icy mais on ne parle point
de Mont^{seigneur} le prince quoy que plusieurs assurent qu'il y a
pour luy un Traicte paroy
On témoigne icy de grandes allegresses pour cette paix de
laquelle la France n'est redouable qu'aux boingx qu'en a voulu
prendre son Eminence

[MdP 4891, fol. 710. 25 April, <https://mia.medici.org/Mia/#/mia/document-entity/54756>]

Considering the possible impact in France, the decision about publication of the treaty was not to be taken lightly, although signs of jubilation or relief were impossible to repress. The newsletter goes on, adding that the Cardinal “has not yet judged that it should be published although this morning the cannon of the Bastille were fired, and by tomorrow we will know part of the details, whereas the indisposition of his Eminence, who has been in his bed for the past eight days, has delayed the assembly that should meet at the Louvre to publicize this peace; whereas in the meantime we are assured that we only keep four places in Artois, which are, Arras, Bethune, Bapaume, and Hesdin....”

Still on the 30th, the public was in the dark, as this Paris newsletter noted:

"From Paris on April 30, 1659. Everyone here is waiting for the publication of the peace which is postponed for reasons which are not known to anyone. The 40 hour prayers that were instated last Sunday ended tonight. All that we have in Artois will remain with us, Arras, Bethune, La Bassée, Lens, L'Isle, Bapaume, and the right that the king of Spain has over Lesdin, Thionville, Danvilliers and Montemedy in Luxembourg, everything that we hold in Roussillon remains with us. Valenza, Mortara in Italy, Roses in Catalonia will be returned in exchange the Spaniards will return Vercelli and give us Cambrai. [...]"

De Paris le 30^e avril 1659 711

Chacun est en l'attente de la publication de la paix
qui est différée pour des raisons que nous ne savons
Chacun les portons de 40 heures qui furent de mauche dernier
ce portés ont finy ce soir /

Car si nous n'avons de l'artois nous demeurera, Arras
Bethune, La Bassée, Lens, L'Isle, Bapaume et le droit que
le Roy d'Espagne a sur le Din /

Thionville, Danvilliers, et Montmedy dans le Luxembourg
Tout ce que nous tenons dans le Roussillon nous demeurera
Valence, Mortara en Italie, Roses en Catalogne, seront rendus
en échange. Les Espagnols rendront Vercelli et nous donneront
Cambrai /

Monsieur le prince, ont luy laissé Roerij, les cathedrales
de Finchamps pour trois ans pendant lesquels selon comme
il se conduira le Roy d'Espagne de grace ou vers luy pour le Restant
du gouvernement et charges /

Ces deux plans sont laissés adieux différents. L'un
par don de Conqueste glauche pour tenir ~~ce~~ lieu de dot
à l'Infante /

Et si quelque tel place de toute la Flandre, même
demoureront à la France soit qu'il y ait enfant ou non ou
deffaut d'hoir mâle venant d'Espagne /

De Bourdeaux du 24^e /

Nous avons la confirmation de l'heureuse arrivée de la flotte
à St. André, et que 15. Navires de l'Espagne ont pris la route
de Cadix cela nous est confirmé de plusieurs lieux /

[MdP 4891, fol. 711 30 April: <https://mia.medici.org/Mia/#/mia/document-entity/54759>]

The information in the 30 April newsletter was important enough for a translation to be made up for circulation to the Italian audience, now found in the same volume in the archive, at folio 717.

Di Parigi il 30 aprile 1659

Siamo qui nell'attesa della publicata della pace che differisce
per le ragioni incognite a tutti. Le preghiere delle 40 hore sono
finite questa sera. Tutto quello che teniamo nell'Artois sarà
nostro. Arras Bethune, Labanà Lens Lille Bapaume, et il ducato che
il Re di Spagna a sepp. ha ordinato —
Thionville Darmoties et Montmedij nel Luxembourg è tutto —
tutto quello che teniamo nel Roussillon sarà suo
Valenza e Morara in Italia, Roda in Catalogna saranno —
restituiti et gli altri di Spagna che restituiranno Perceil, e ne
ne daranno Cambrai —
Le vilij. Prencipi di Fondi Libera lasciati Rocroy il castello
et Lincampo per 3 anni. Intanto secondo che si governerà il Re
userà di grazia verso di lui per il resto de suoi Governatori, e
Cariche —
Vene due Piastre saranno lasciate a due differenti titoli l'uno
di ducato di Longueville et l'altro di ducato di Lorena et d'ora dell'Infante
il ducato de tutto il Piastro di tutta la Francia medesima resterà alla
Francia se de li habbia figlioli, o no. In mancanza di herede
masculi Venendo di spaz —
Bordeaux 24. d.

Habbiamo confirmatione della felicissima annata della flotta a.
cont. e che 11 Vascelli delli Particolari hanno pigliato a Bord
Madise, ne habbiamo conferme di più luoghi —

<https://mia.medici.org/Mia/#/mia/document-entity/54759>

From the newsletters to the newspapers, however, in this demi-monde between script and print, even more time would pass; so that the French *Gazette* takes notice only in the issue of 3 May, referring however, to letters received a week before; to wit:

[MdP 4891 fol. 687 <https://mia.medici.org/Mia/index.html#/mia/document-entity/54739>]

"On the 26th of last month, the King sent his Letters to the Vicars General of our Archbishop, saying that His Majesty finding himself in such a situation for the glory of God, and the good of his State, needed a particular blessing from Heaven, and wanted them to make the Churches of this city and of the Diocese of Paris recite the Forty Hours Prayers in the streets: and this began the next day, by the exposure of the Blessed Sacrament, and continued for the next two days, with so much greater piety of all the People, considering that they had the example of their Sovereign...."

Timing indeed was everything, these examples show. But timing depended upon numerous variables, which we are discovering every day as we attempt to recover the lost world of early modern news.

FURTHER READING

Bertrand Haan. *Une paix pour l'éternité: La négociation du traité du Cateau-Cambrésis*. Bibliothèque de la Casa de Velázquez 49. Madrid: Casa de Velázquez, 2010